

DESIGN FOR A NEW 25MW GRID CONNECTED SOLAR PV PLANT AT JAISALMER, RAJASTHAN

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Abstract—There are various challenges faced due to the usage of conventional energy sources. Current concerns include issues such as non-renewability, rising prices, their dependency on external imports of fuel and the associated security risks, as well as increasing concerns of environmental degradation. Solar power generation in India -as a sustainable source of energy- has risen exponentially in the past decade as an attractive and feasible option. Rajasthan has high potential for harnessing solar power with around 300-330 clear sunny days along with large amount of relatively flat and undeveloped land. In this paper we have simulated an on-grid solar power plant with a capacity of 25 MW for Jaisalmer. The study includes a detailed simulation of the plant using a PC software package PVsyst and a comprehensive analysis of all major losses incurred at the plant level.

Keywords—PVsyst, Rajasthan, Solar power plant, Renewable energy sources.

I. INTRODUCTION

The energy generated using solar has massively increased over the last few years and is expected to have a double digit growth in the years to come. The Indian state Rajasthan is one of the states where the potential for harnessing solar energy is extremely large. Geographically, Rajasthan is uniquely placed to tap solar radiation with 300 to 330 clear sunny days and average daily solar incidence of 5-7 kWh/m²/day.[1]

The basic components of a utility scale grid connected solar PV plant mainly include:

A. DC side:

Solar PV modules, mounting structures, tracking mechanism, DC Cables, String monitoring box pyranometer.

B. AC side:

Solar inverter, AC Circuit breaker, Multi-functional electric meters, Transformers.

C. Other components:

Pyranometer, Weather monitoring system, SCADA.

In this paper we have simulated a design for a new 25MW grid connected solar PV plant at Jaisalmer, Rajasthan using PVsyst software.

PVsyst software is one of the simulation software developed to estimate the performance of the solar power plant by importing meteo data from many different sources as well as personnel data. This software evaluates the performance of grid-connected, stand-alone and pumping systems based on the specified module selection. The program accurately predicts the system yields computed using detailed hourly simulation data.

The main components selected in PVsyst software for simulation are: Si-Poly solar module- JA Solar-JAP6 (BK) 60/245/3BB-240 Wp; 3Ø Solar Inverter- Bosch Power Tec GmbH- Bosch Power Tec GmbH-1000KWac

II. PARAMETERS CONSIDERED FOR DESIGN PROCESS

A. Location Details

1. Co-ordinates: Latitude (N or S) and Longitude (E or W)
2. Topological, climatic and geographical features.

B. Technical details

1. Type of system: On grid or off grid
2. PV Module technology: Mono/Poly/Thin-film
3. Module Capacity: Wp (Output wattage) or make
4. Inverter: Type, Capacity and make

C. Other Criteria

1. Pitch selection-Pitch is the minimum distance between two modules to avoid any effect of shadowing under all weather conditions and sun positions throughout the day. Pitch selection is done with respect to tilt angle to limit the shading losses. The shading losses should be within 1.5%.
2. Modules are “Free” mounted with air ducts, and cooling is done due to air circulation around the modules. 24 modules are connected in series for one string, and each string is connected in parallel to one String Monitoring Box (SMB).
3. Auxiliaries are not considered for initial analysis
4. Inverters are selected so that under loading and overloading (DC to AC) ratio is in acceptable range. The number of Inverters selected are 25 1MW inverters.

Figure 1 Overall layout of inverter connection

III. DESIGN PROCESS

A. Site selection

Parameters considered were the amount of incident solar radiation, availability of vacant land for present as well as its future development, site accessibility from nearby highways, for minimization of transportation costs. Distance from transmission lines was also minimized.

Rajasthan has insolation of 5-7 KWh/m²/day, mostly arid, largely level land as well as good governmental support for renewable power generation.

Using GIS software in an exclusion method [1], Jaisalmer, an area with a maximum summer temperature of 43°C and the largest area, 180.37 x 106 m² in the region was identified. The latitude is 26.92°N, 70.90°E and was selected due to fulfilment of site selection parameters.

The coordinates of the site are then entered in PVsyst to access Meteorom data for the area which includes Global Irradiance, Diffuse Irradiance, and temperature and wind velocity of the site.

Figure 2 Satellite view of the location of the site

B. Panel chosen

Thin film technology has a higher performance ratio compared to Si/Poly-Si but greater degradation losses over time. Poly-Si panels are preferred, especially for PV plants set over a large area.

For 1 KWp of power from a Polycrystalline Silicon Panel an area of 8m² is required [2], so an average module area of around 183208 m² is needed.

A Poly-Si PV panel of 245Wp is suggested for use at the plant.

C. Selection of Optimum tilt

Parameters such as cell material, cell temperature, energy conversion efficiency and the maximum power point tracking, along with solar irradiation affect the output of a solar panel. In order to maximize the amount of solar irradiation that falls on the panel it is necessary that the panel is inclined at the optimum tilt angle. The ideal position for facing of PV arrays in Rajasthan is due south, but slight deviations are allowed. 92% of the annual solar radiation is well received by an un-shaded PV array tilted at latitude and facing +/- 450 away from due south. The average optimum tilt angle can be estimated to 39.5° for winter months (December-March) and 11.9° for summer months (April-November). [3]

The tilt angle of 40° and 12° is taken as it gives the maximum output for that value.

D. Tilt arrangement

Single Axis Trackers show better performance in comparison to Seasonal Axis arrangements in general. However for an incremental gain in received insolation using tracking technology there is also a corresponding increase in cost per Wp. With an analysis considering irradiation received, and gain in global incident irradiation received vs cost per Wp, it can be observed that a seasonal axis tracker is preferred for North Indian states [4]

Figure 3 Tilt arrangement

IV. DETAILED LOSS ANALYSIS

A. Panel level Losses

1. LID (light induced degradation)

Initial degradation for solar PV module occurs in the very first hours of operation on the actual site when module is exposed to sunlight. After certain period of time the power output of the module stabilizes.

2. Mismatch loss

Mismatch losses are caused by the interconnection of solar cells or modules which do not have identical wattages or power output. This is because in a string of modules the lowest current drives the current of the whole string because of the material property of silicon which is used for PV module manufacturing. The mismatch losses are constant.

3. Soiling losses

Accumulation of dirt and its effect on system performance is an uncertainty which strongly depends on the environment of the system, raining conditions. Soiling losses vary dynamically according to the geography. In Rajasthan the power loss can be up to 3%. This loss can be reduced by increasing frequency of module cleaning.

4. IAM losses

The incidence effect (the designated term is IAM, for "Incidence Angle Modifier") corresponds to the decrease of the irradiance really reaching the PV cells surface, with respect to irradiance under normal incidence. This decrease is mainly due to reflections on the glass cover, which increases with the incidence angle. The transmission loss is a general phenomenon, due to the reflection and transmission of the sun's ray at each material interface (air-glass, glass-EVA, EVA-cell), as well as some absorption in the glass. This arises for any incidence ray. For normal incidence, the reflection is of the order of 5%, and is included in the measured STC performance. The IAM only concerns the angular dependency of this effect, i.e. it is normalized to the transmission at perpendicular incidence (0° incidence angle).

5. Aging

The main parts of a PV system subjected to ageing are:

- The PV module (long-term degradation), eventually the inverters, which have sometimes to be repaired or replaced, wiring elements, lightning surge protectors, etc.
- The PV module degradation gives rise to a progressive loss of efficiency, which is characterized by a "Degradation Loss factor"

People often use the Manufacturer's warranty as loss reference when designing PV systems, which is usually a loss of efficiency of around 20% after 25 years.

Figure 4 Total panel level losses

B. Losses due to Auxiliaries

The auxiliary energy is any electrical energy subtracted from the energy pushed to the grid for powering equipment onsite. Auxiliary losses are not considered for initial design procedure.

C. Unavailability Losses

System unavailability is defined as a fraction of time, or a number of days. It can also occur during the down-time for periodic maintenance of the system. As this is usually unpredictable, it is possible to define specific periods of unavailability of the system, and also to create these periods in a random way. The effective energy loss depends on the season and the weather during the unavailability periods.

D. Ohmic losses

Ohmic losses are defined by the formula: $P_w = R_w * I_{sc}^2$

Where: R_w : global wiring resistance of the full system, I_{sc} : Short circuit current.

We assume the global wiring resistance R_w which is an ohmic loss ratio of the system as a default value of 1.5%. This ratio diminishes linearly with the output current. So ohmic losses are much less than STC are much lower during plant working condition

E. Cable Losses

- The AC cable losses-They are the losses that occur in cables running between the inverter output and the injection point, here transformer, which is stepped up for the required voltage to be injected to the grid. They are mainly caused due to skin effect and dielectric losses.
- The DC cable losses-They are the losses that occur mainly due to the power losses (I^2R losses) and voltage drop through the cable.

F. Transformer Losses

- The iron losses (due to hysteresis and eddy currents in the core) are considered as a constant loss.
- The ohmic losses either in the primary or in the secondary windings. These may be represented by an equivalent resistance, and the loss will be computed as $R \cdot I^2$ during the simulation.

Therefore the yearly resistive loss will always be lower (in percentage) than the nominal loss at STC.

G. Inverter Losses

The power losses in an inverter consist of switching losses and conduction losses as well as MPPT errors. Losses from inverter maximum power point tracking (MPPT) errors are a constant source of uncertainty in PV performance modeling. MPPT efficiency comprises both of static MPPT efficiency, which quantifies the array power captured under stable conditions, and dynamic MPPT efficiency, which applies under changing irradiance and temperature.

Its value is typically limited to less than 1% in a good solar inverter.

Figure 5 Power sizing of inverter output distribution

V. DESIGN OVERVIEW

For a PV Field Orientation with a seasonal tilt: summer/winter $12^\circ/40^\circ$, azimuth 0° and PV modules Model JAP6(BK) 60-245/3BB, with Nominal Power (P_{nom}) 245 Wp used. Each string consists of 48 solar panels connected in series-parallel combination using Y-connectors. Each structure consists of 24 panels.

The number of PV modules in series are 24, and in parallel are 4340 (strings). The Total number of PV modules are 104160. The total PV array module area occupies around 170317 m^2 with a cell area of 152090 m^2 . The Array P_{nom} at (STC) is 25519 kWp, 25 inverters of Inverter Model BPT-IS 1000 with P_{nom} 1000 kW with 25000 kW ac total capacity are used.

For a yearly horizontal global irradiation of 1999 kWh/m², the produced Energy of the system is 43849 MWh/year, with a specific production of 1718 kWh/kWp/year. The Performance Ratio (PR) of the system is 74.40 %

Figure 6 PV plant schema

Figure 7 Schema representing connection of stings to the inverters

Figure 8 Daily system output energy

Figure 9 Yearly Normalized production and loss factor

Figure 10 Water flow diagram

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A performance study of 25 MW peak grid connected solar photovoltaic power plant installed was evaluated on annual basis. The following conclusions are drawn from the study:

- Maximum total energy generation of 4021 MW h was observed in the month of March and lowest total energy generation of 3303 MW h was observed in the month of August.
- 25 MW solar power plant has been operating with good amount of PR and CUF. The plant has been in operation and feeding energy to grid at an available percentage of almost 99%.

The study provides an insight to identify the location and suitable PV technology for large scale deployment of solar photovoltaic system in India. This information is useful in evaluating the operational benefits of the plant based on the net energy output.

The monitored data and operating experience of PV system can be applied for future large scale projects.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

This analysis can be used as one of the initial stages in designing and planning a PV grid connected system.

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REFERENCES

- [1]Khan, Ghazanfar, and Shikha Rathi. "Optimal site selection for solar PV power plant in an Indian state using geographical information system (GIS)." International Journal of Emerging Engineering Research and Technology 2.7 (2014): 260-266.
- [2] "Comparative Assessment of Technologies: Crystalline PV vs. Thin Film Solar", WORK Report.
- [3]Maru, Navaneet & Vajpai, Jayashri & Khyani, Harish & Prof, Assoc. (2016). "Estimation of Optimum Tilt Angle and Orientation of Photovoltaic Panels in Bap-Rajasthan."
- [4] "Performance of Solar Power Plants in India", Central Electricity Regulatory Commission New Delhi, February, 2011